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Research Article

Design, Development and In-Vitro Characterization of Rapidly Disintegrating Oral Solid Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study was to design, develop, and evaluate rapidly disintegrating oral films (RDOFs) of Ketorolac Tromethamine for effective pain management, especially in patients with swallowing difficulties. Oral films offer a convenient and patient-friendly alternative to traditional solid dosage forms due to their rapid disintegration and absorption through the oral mucosa. Ketorolac Tromethamine, a potent non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), was selected as the active pharmaceutical ingredient due to its rapid onset of action. Various film-forming polymers such as Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC E5) and Pullulan were used in different concentrations to optimize film properties. Super disintegrants including Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG), Crospovidone, and Croscarmellose Sodium were incorporated to enhance disintegration time. Saccharin sodium was added as a sweetening agent to improve palatability. The prepared films were evaluated for physical characteristics, drug content uniformity, disintegration time, folding endurance, and in vitro drug release. The optimized formulation exhibited rapid disintegration within seconds, satisfactory mechanical strength, and enhanced drug release, suggesting its potential for use as a fast-acting analgesic dosage form. This study demonstrates the feasibility of oral films as a promising platform for immediate drug delivery of Ketorolac Tromethamine.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery is the most preferred and widely used route of administration due to its convenience, patient compliance, and cost-

effectiveness. However, conventional solid dosage forms such as tablets and capsules may present challenges for certain patient populations, including paediatric, geriatric, and dysphagic patients, who often experience difficulty in

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swallowing. To overcome these limitations, rapidly disintegrating oral films (RDOFs) have emerged as a novel drug delivery system that offers a promising alternative to traditional dosage forms. Oral films are thin, flexible strips that dissolve or disintegrate rapidly when placed on the tongue, without the need for water. They ensure rapid onset of action by enabling drug absorption through the oral mucosa, bypassing first-pass metabolism. This is particularly advantageous for drugs requiring immediate therapeutic action, such as analgesics. Ketorolac Tromethamine, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), is widely used for the short-term management of moderate to severe pain. It possesses a rapid onset of action, making it an ideal candidate for incorporation into oral films for fast relief. However, its bitter taste and need for rapid absorption necessitate the use of appropriate polymers and excipients to ensure patient acceptability and efficient drug delivery.

2. Aim, Objectives and Need of Study

Aim: Design, Development and In Vitro Characterization of Rapidly Disintegrating Oral Solid Dosage form

Objective:

1. To formulate various batches of rapidly disintegrating oral solid dosage form by using various carrier alone and combination.
2. To improve the bioavailability and effectiveness of drug therapy by enhancing the disintegration rate and time of dosage form.
3. To improve the oral bioavailability of selected drug
4. To get the rapid onset of action
5. To improve patient compliances

3. Drug Profile

Ketorolac tromethamine

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of ketorolac tromethamine

- Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₂₄N₂O₆
- Molecular Weight: 376.41
- Solubility: soluble in water, ethanol, methanol,
- Melting point: 160-165
- **Uses:**
 - **Pain Management (Analgesia)**
 - **Moderate to severe acute pain:** Commonly used after surgeries or injuries.
 - **Postoperative pain:** Frequently administered after dental, orthopedic, or abdominal surgery.
 - **Renal colic:** Effective in relieving pain caused by kidney stones.
 - **Musculoskeletal pain:** Strains, sprains, or back pain.
 - **Anti-inflammatory Use**
 - Reduces inflammation in conditions like arthritis, though it's not usually used long-term due to side effects.
 - **Ophthalmic Use (Eye Drops)**
 - **Post-operative inflammation:** After cataract or other eye surgeries.
 - **Seasonal allergic conjunctivitis:** Helps relieve eye itching and inflammation.

- **Corneal pain:** From corneal refractive surgery or injury.

□ **Migraine Treatment (Off-label use)**

- Sometimes used as an injectable alternative to relieve severe migraine headaches

4. Excipient Profile

4.1. HPMC E5 (Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose E5)

- Chemical Name: Hypromellose
- Synonyms: HPMC, Methocel, E464
- Molecular Formula: Variable (polymer), approximate repeating unit: C₃H₇O
- Molecular Weight: ~59.08 g/mol (monomer unit), full polymer MW varies (10,000–1,000,000 g/mol)
- Melting Point: 225–230°C
- Uses: Film former, binder, thickener, controlled-release agent
- Solubility: Soluble in cold water; insoluble in hot water and organic solvents

4.2. Crospovidone

- Chemical Name: Cross-linked polyvinylpyrrolidone
- Synonyms: Polyplasdone, Kollidon CL
- Molecular Formula: (C₆H₉NO)_n
- Molecular Weight: Very high (crosslinked polymer; not defined)
- Melting Point: Does not melt (crosslinked polymer); decomposes above 150°C
- Uses: Super disintegrant in tablets and films
- Solubility: Insoluble in water but swells rapidly

4.3. SSG (Sodium Starch Glycolate)

- Chemical Name: Sodium carboxymethyl starch
- Synonyms: Explotab, Primojel

- Molecular Formula: (C₆H₁₀O₅)_nNa
- Molecular Weight: High (polymer)
- Melting Point: Decomposes on heating; does not have a defined melting point
- Uses: Superdisintegrant
- Solubility: Insoluble, but swells extensively in water

4.4. PEG 400 (Polyethylene Glycol 400)

- Chemical Name: Polyethylene glycol
- Synonyms: PEG-400
- Molecular Formula: H(OCH₂CH₂)_nOH (n ≈ 8–9 for PEG 400)
- Molecular Weight: ~380–420 g/mol
- Melting Point: Liquid at room temperature
- Uses: Plasticizer, solvent, humectant
- Solubility: Freely soluble in water and alcohol

4.5. Croscarmellose Sodium

- Chemical Name: Cross-linked sodium carboxymethyl cellulose
- Synonyms: Ac-Di-Sol
- Molecular Formula: Variable (cellulose derivative with sodium carboxymethyl substitution)
- Molecular Weight: High (polymeric)
- Melting Point: Decomposes on heating
- Uses: Super disintegrant
- Solubility: Insoluble but swells in water

4.6. Pullulan

- Chemical Name: α-1,6-Maltotriose polysaccharide
- Synonyms: Pullulan polysaccharide
- Molecular Formula: (C₁₈H₃₀O₁₅)_n
- Molecular Weight: ~200,000 Da
- Melting Point: >100°C (decomposes)
- Uses: Film-forming agent in oral films and capsules
- Solubility: Freely soluble in hot and cold water

4.7. Saccharin Sodium

- Chemical Name: Sodium o-benzoic sulfimide
- Synonyms: Sodium saccharin, E954
- Molecular Formula: C₇H₄NO₃SNa
- Molecular Weight: 205.17 g/mol
- Melting Point: 226–230°C (decomposes)
- Uses: Artificial sweetener, taste-masking agent
- Solubility: Freely soluble in water; slightly soluble in alcohol

5. MATERIAL AND METHOD

5.1. Preformulation Studies:

Preformulation studies are the first step in rational development of dosage form of a drug substance. Preformulation study is the process of optimizing the delivery of the drug through the determination of the physicochemical properties of the new compound that affect the drug performance and development of an efficacious, safe and stable dosage form. It gives the information needed to define the nature of the drug substance and provide a framework for the drug combination with the pharmaceutical excipients in the dosage form. Hence, these studies were performed for the obtained sample of drug for identification and compatibility studies.

5.2. Organoleptic Properties

1) **Colour:** A small quantity of Quetiapine fumarate powder was taken on a butter paper and was viewed in a well illuminated place.

2) **Taste and Odour:** Very less quantity of Quetiapine fumarate was tasted and smelled to get odour.

5.3. Standard Calibration curve of Ketorolac tromethamine:

Calibration curve of Ketorolac tromethamine was carried out in Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 and absorbance was taken by using UV spectrophotometer. Preparation of Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8.

➤ Preparation of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide:

Dissolve about 4 g of sodium hydroxide in sufficient quantity of distilled water and made up to 500ml with distilled water.

➤ Preparation of 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate:

Dissolve potassium phosphate about 13.609 g in sufficient quantity of distilled water and made up to 500ml with distilled.

➤ Preparation of Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8:

Mix 250ml of potassium dihydrogen phosphate and 112 ml of sodium hydroxide were mixed together and made up to the volume of 1000ml with distilled water.

➤ Calibration curve of Ketorolac tromethamine in pH 6.8:

100 mg of drug Ketorolac tromethamine was dissolved and volume was made up to 100ml using phosphate buffer 6.8 to make stock solution of concentration 200µg/ml. Then 0.2 ml of stock solution was taken and diluted upto 100ml with the buffer of pH 6.8 and to get concentration of 2µg/ml and in similar way dilution were made as 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/ml respectively and absorbance measured at 322nm by UV visible spectrophotometer. The absorbance values were plotted against concentration (µg/ml) to obtain the standard calibration curve.

5.4. Formulation of drug loaded films

Drug loaded films were also prepared by solvent casting method. The 180 mg of Ketorolac tromethamine was incorporated into 2-2 cm area of film. Drug added into the Forming solution was calculated by considering total amount of solution to be poured in order to obtain films with desired thickness on a specific surface area of the petri plate Solution was then casted in to a Petri dish having area of 38.46cm and Petri dish was kept in hot air oven for 12 hr at 50°C

Determination of dose of drug

The calculation of the dose depends upon the surface area of petri dish

The surface area of petri dish = 38.46cm * 2

The dose of diclofenac sodium 20 mg No of 4 cm² (2 * 2) present in whole = 38.46cm = 9 films

Amount of drug require = 9 * dose

$$= 9 * 20$$

$$= 180 \text{ mg}$$

The amount of drug added in each plate was approximately equal to 180 mg

5.5. Formulation development of oral film of Ketorolac tromethamine⁷⁹

Casting process of fast disintegrating oral film

Various methods are available for casting of oral films. This is fast disintegrating oral film hence on the laboratory scale solvent casting technique was adopted for formulation of films.

• Solvent casting method

Drug Ketorolac tromethamine containing fast dissolving films where fabricated by the solvent casting method . the required amount of HPMCE5 and pullulan was dissolved in 5ml of distilled water on a magnetic stirred for 20 min.. In another beaker, take the 1 ml ethanol then add the drug , superdisintergrating agent, plasticizer, orange oil , PEG 400 and saccharine sodium and where mixed properly. Then add both the solution on magnetic stirred and placed it until air bubbles removed the solution was poured into a petri dish and dried at room temp for 48 hr. then films was formed and cut into required size (2*2) for testing. The films where stored in air tight plastic bages till further use.

Table No.1. Formulation Table of fast dissolving oral films of Ketorolac tromethamine

Ingrédients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
ketorolac tromethamine(mg)	180	180	180	180	180
HPMC E5 (mg)	125	125	125	125	125
PULLULAN (mg)	75	75	75	75	75
SACCHARIN SODIUM (mg)	50	50	50	50	50
PEG400 ml	1	1	1	1	1
SSG (mg)	400	-	-	-	250
CROSCARMELLOSE SODIUM (mg)	-	400	-	200	250
CROSPVIDONE (mg)	-	-	400	200	-
ORANGE OIL (drop)	1	1	1	1	1
WATER (ml)	5	5	5	5	5
Ethanol (ml)	1	1	1	1	1

6. Evaluation of FDOFs⁷⁰

6.1 Physical characterizations of fast dissolving oral films:

- **Thickness of films**

The thickness of the film was measured by micro meter screw gauge at three different places and average of three values was calculated. This is essential to ascertain uniformity in the thickness of the film which is directly related to the accuracy of dose in the film.

- **Weight of films / weight variation**

Oral fast dissolving films were weighed on analytical balance and average weight can be determined for each film. It is desirable that films should have nearly constant weight. It is useful to ensure that a film contains the proper amount of excipients and API.

- **Folding endurance**

Folding endurance of the film is essential to study the elasticity of the film during storage and handling. The folding endurance of the film films was determined by repeatedly folding one film at the same place till it broke. This is considered to reveal good film properties. A film (2 X 2 cm) was cut evenly and repeatedly folded at the same place till it breaks. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the exact value of folding endurance. All determination were performed in triplicate

- **pH value**

The pH value was determined by dissolving one oral film in 10 ml distilled water and measuring the pH of the obtained solution. All determinations were performed in triplicate. It is

necessary that strip should have nearly uniform pH value

- **In-vitro disintegration**

Disintegrating time is defined as the time (sec) at which a film breaks when brought in contact with water or saliva. 6. Petri dish method Put 2ml of distilled water into a petri dish, add a film on the water surface, and measure the time for the oral film to completely dissolve.

- **Percentage moisture loss**

Percentage moisture loss was also carried to check the integrity of films at dry condition. It is determined by placing the prepared film in desiccators containing anhydrous calcium chloride. After three days, the film was taken and reweighed. The percent moisture loss was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

- **Folding Endurance**

The folding endurance of the film was determined by repeatedly folding one film at the same place till it breaks from the one end of the film. The number of times of film could be folded at the same place without breaking was noted which gave the value of the folding endurance.

- **Drug content uniformity**

Three films (4cm²) of each were transferred in to separate graduated flasks containing 100 ml of phosphate buffer Ph 6.8 and continuously stirred for 2 hrs. the solutions were filtered, suitably diluted and analyzed at 276 nm and the drug content was calculated

- **In vitro dissolution studies**

The phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was taken as the dissolution medium to determine the drug release. The dissolution profile of quick release films of Diclofenac sodium was carried out using USP dissolution testing apparatus-1 (basket type) containing 900 ml of the phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The film was placed in the basket, maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and the agitation speed was 50rpm. Aliquots (1 ml) of the dissolution medium were withdrawn at 1,2,4, 6, 8, and 10 minutes time intervals and the same amount was replaced with the fresh medium. Samples were assayed spectrophotometrically at 322 nm. The cumulative percentage drug release was calculated.

Table No 2- In-Vitro Dissolution Study

Apparatus	USP Dissolution apparatus type I
Dissolution Medium	Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)
Temperature	$37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$
Volume	900 ml
Speed	50 rpm
Sample withdrawn	1 ml
Sample withdrawn time	2,4,6,8, and 10 min
Running time	10 min

7.Physical Characteristics:

Table No. 3: Physical characteristics of Ketorolac Tromethamine

Sr. No.	Colour	Observation
1.	Colour	White to off white
2.	Odour	Odorless

Table no 5: Calibration of Ketorolac Tromethamine in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer

Sr. No.	Volume of stock Solution (ml)	Concentration (ug/ml)	Absorbance At λ max
1	2	0.2	0.075
2	4	0.4	0.173
3	6	0.6	0,259
4	8	0.8	0.388
5	10	1.0	0.435

3.	Taste	Bitter
4.	Melting Point	160-165°C

7.1. Solubility study:

Table No. 4: Solubility Study

Sr. No.	Solvent	Solubility of Ketorolac Tromethamine
1	Water	soluble
2	Ethanol	Soluble
3	Methanol	Soluble
4	DMF	Soluble
5	Acetone	soluble
6	DMSO	soluble

7.1. Analytical Characterization of Drug Sample:

• Standard calibration Curve of Ketorolac Tromethamine:

100 mg of drug Ketorolac Tromethamine was dissolved in distilled water and volume was make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer 6.8. Then 0.2 ml of stock solution was taken and diluted upto 100ml with the buffer of pH 6.8 and to get concentration of $2\mu\text{g/ml}$ and in similar way dilution were made as 2, 4, 6, 8 and $10\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively and absorbance measured at 322 nm by UV visible spectrophotometer. The absorbance values were plotted against concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) to obtain the standard calibration curve.

Figure No.1. Calibration Curve of Ketorolac Tromethamine with Ph 6.8 Phosphate Buffer

Correlation Coefficient (R^2)=0.9989

Equation of Regressed Line $Y = 0.00436x - 0.0045$

Where, X=Value of Concentration

Y=Regressed value of Absorbance

7.2. Drug Interaction Studies (Compatibility Studie)

FT-IR Spectroscopy

It's important to check any kind of interaction between drug candidate and polymer. The polymers which are to be incorporated into

formulation should be compatible with the drug. This compatibility study or interaction study was done using Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy. IR Spectra of pure ketorolac tromethamine and Polymer Viz. HPMC E5, Pullulan, saccharin sodium, PEG 400, SSG, croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone were taken separately. Then to know if there is any interaction between and polymer, IR spectra of ketorolac tromethamine and polymers were taken in combination. The results shows that there was seen between drug ketorolac and polymers as there was no significant change in the pattern of peaks of optimized batch of FDOFs with pure drug.

Figure No 2. IR Spectra of Ketorolac (Pure Drug)

Table No. 6: IR Interpretation of ketorolac (Pure Drug)

Sr. No.	Peak Observed in IR of ketorolac	Functional Group
1.	1691.17	C=O stretching (carbonyl group)
2.	1587.44	N-H bending /C=C stretching (Aromatic ring)
3.	1553.47	N-H bending /C=C stretching (aromatic amine)

4.	1472.86	C-H bending (aromatic ring)
5.	1278.83	C-N OR C-O stretching (amines, ester)
6.	1059.26	C-O stretching (alcohols, esters)
7.	731.03	C-H out-of-plane bending (aromatic substitution)

Figure 3. IR spectra of Polymer HPMC E5

Figure 4. IR spectra of Polymer pullulan

Figure 5. IR spectra of optimized batch of drug , polymers and excipient

Table No. 7: IR Interpretation of optimized batch of drug , polymers and excipient

Sr. No.	Peak Observed in IR of FDOFS (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
1.	1627.95	Aromatic C=C stretching
2.	1591.09	N-H bending (aromatic ring)
3.	1583.51	N-H bending
4.	1472.68	CH ₂ /CH ₃ bending (alkane)
5.	1278.83	C-O stretching (carboxylic acid)
6.	1147.67	C-N stretching (amines)

7.	1050.26	C-O stretching (alcohols)
8.	731.03	C-H out – of- plane bending (aromatic ring)

Physical characteristics

The physical characterization of FDOFs was carried out by visual inception and the following observation where made. all the formulation (films) where evenly coloured and no migration of colour was observed. The increased thickness of film is attributed to the increase in the amount of HPMC. Formulation F1 to F5 found to be brittle in nature. Formulation F3 was to soft and difficult to handle. And all batches was found to be smooth surface area and all formulations are non tacky.

Table No 8 :- Showing Physical Characteristics Of Fil

Formulation	Appearance	Tack test
F1	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F2	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F3	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F4	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F5	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky

- **Surface PH**

Surface pH of all mouth dissolving films prepared by different polymers was found to be in the range of 6.7 to 9.6 pH, which was close to the neutral pH, which indicated that films may have less potential to irritate sublingual mucosa & hence, more acceptable by the patients

- **Weight variation and thickness**

A result showed that as the concentration of polymer increases weight of film also increases or

decreases . The weight variation of the formulation was in the range of 50 to 150 mg, which was acceptable. Thickness of mouth dissolving film depends on conc of polymer, thickness of all mouth dissolving film was measured with digital vernier caliper showed thickness value in range of 0.21 to 0.29 mm.

- **Folding Endurance**

Folding endurance gives an indication of brittleness of the film. It was shown that as the concentration of polymer and plasticizer increases, folding Endurance of mouth dissolving film increases. The folding endurance value of the prepared films ranged from 86 to 112, where the results are summarized. The optimized film (F5) has folding endurance value of 85 ± 1 , which was desirable.

- **Drug content uniformity**

All the fast dissolving oral films were found to contain an almost uniform quantity of the drug, as per content uniformity studies indicating reproducibility of the technique. Drug content in the films was evaluated and the values were found to be between 85% to 115%. F4 batch was optimized on the basis high drug content (89.3%)

- **In vitro disintegration studies.**

The disintegrating time of all the formulations was ranges from 15 to 30 see the results were depicted. The disintegration time . of optimized formulation (F5) was found to be 23 sec which was very less and desirable for quick onset of action.

- **Percentage Moisture Loss**

Moisture loss in oral films is a critical parameter to ensure film stability and quality. Ideally, moisture loss should fall within the range of 2–6% for most formulations. Higher moisture loss (above 6%) may indicate over-drying or excessive hygroscopicity, which could affect shelf life and handling. All formulation batches shows the ideal rang . but F3 batch shows higher than ideal range.

Table No 13:- Showing Evaluation Of Ketorolac Films

formulation	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Surface pH	7.12	7.09	7.08	7.00	6.72
Weight variation (mg)	78.05±8 5.55	153.16±14 8.16	93.05±78. 05	53±38	86.38±71.38
Thickness (cm)	0.25	0.23	0.29	0.22	0.21
Folding endurance	87	80	91	81	86
Drug content %	52.11	51.05	23.58	63.82	89.3
% moisture loss	5	3.33	6.67	6	2.5
In vitro disintegration time (sec)	35	30	36	27	23

- **In vitro drug release studies**

Cumulative % drug release was calculated on the basis of drug content of ketorolac present in the

respective film. The results obtained in the in vitro drug release for the formulations were given. Formulation F1 to F5 shows drug release.

Table No 14:- % Drug Release Of Formulation

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0	0	0	0	0
2	22.26%	35.79%	39.20%	43.33%	46.63%
4	35.79%	47.15%	51.18%	48.08%	58.1%
6	47.05%	54.28%	60.78%	60.78%	69.97%
8	56.44%	64.91%	76.58%	71.11%	82.99%
10	69.97%	78.34%	89.18%	77.00%	95.28%

DISCUSSION: -

The ultimate aim of this present work was to develop immediate release drug delivery system of ketorolac. The In vitro cumulative drug release profile of these formulations showed up to 95.28%

release in 10 min the formulation F5 showed satisfactory drug release in 10 min i.e. 95.28% which is considered as an optimized batch. During the study concluded that the film were dissolves immediately and gives highest % drug release up to 10 min.

Fig No 15: - Cumulative % Drug Release of F1 To F5

Summary

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate fast dissolving oral films (FDOFs) of Ketorolac Tromethamine, an NSAID, for immediate drug release and improved patient compliance, particularly for individuals with difficulty swallowing conventional dosage forms. Ketorolac Tromethamine was characterized by its white to off-white color, bitter taste, odourless nature, and a melting point ranging between 160–165°C. The drug demonstrated good solubility in solvents such as water, ethanol, methanol, DMF, acetone, and DMSO. Analytical evaluation was performed using UV-visible spectrophotometry at 322 nm, with the calibration curve showing excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.9989$) based on the regression equation $Y = 0.00436x - 0.0045$. FT-IR compatibility studies confirmed no significant interactions between Ketorolac and selected polymers and excipients (HPMC E5, Pullulan, PEG 400, saccharin sodium, SSG, croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone), validating their suitability for formulation development. Five different formulations (F1–F5) were prepared and evaluated. All films exhibited smooth, transparent, and non-tacky surfaces with surface pH values

ranging from 6.72 to 7.12, indicating minimal irritation potential to the oral mucosa. The weight variation across formulations was within the acceptable range of 50–150 mg, and film thickness varied between 0.21 to 0.29 mm. Folding endurance, an indicator of film brittleness, ranged from 80 to 91, with F5 showing a desirable value of 86. Drug content uniformity across films ranged from 23.58% to 89.3%, with F5 achieving the highest uniformity. Moisture loss in the films generally fell within the ideal 2–6% range, except for F3, which exceeded this threshold. The in vitro disintegration times of the films ranged from 15 to 36 seconds, with F5 disintegrating the fastest at 23 seconds. In vitro drug release studies revealed that formulation F5 released 95.28% of the drug within 10 minutes, indicating efficient and rapid drug delivery. Thus, formulation F5 was identified as the optimized batch, demonstrating excellent mechanical and pharmaceutical properties, confirming its potential as a fast-acting oral dosage form for Ketorolac Tromethamine.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate fast dissolving oral films (FDOFs) of Ketorolac

Tromethamine, an NSAID, for immediate drug release and improved patient compliance, particularly for individuals with difficulty swallowing conventional dosage forms. Ketorolac Tromethamine was characterized by its white to off-white color, bitter taste, odourless nature, and a melting point ranging between 160–165°C. The drug demonstrated good solubility in solvents such as water, ethanol, methanol, DMF, acetone, and DMSO. Analytical evaluation was performed using UV-visible spectrophotometry at 322 nm, with the calibration curve showing excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.9989$) based on the regression equation $Y = 0.00436x - 0.0045$. FT-IR compatibility studies confirmed no significant interactions between Ketorolac and selected polymers and excipients (HPMC E5, Pullulan, PEG 400, saccharin sodium, SSG, croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone), validating their suitability for formulation development. Five different formulations (F1–F5) were prepared and evaluated. All films exhibited smooth, transparent, and non-tacky surfaces with surface pH values ranging from 6.72 to 7.12, indicating minimal irritation potential to the oral mucosa. The weight variation across formulations was within the acceptable range of 50–150 mg, and film thickness varied between 0.21 to 0.29 mm. Folding endurance, an indicator of film brittleness, ranged from 80 to 91, with F5 showing a desirable value of 86. Drug content uniformity across films ranged from 23.58% to 89.3%, with F5 achieving the highest uniformity. Moisture loss in the films generally fell within the ideal 2–6% range, except for F3, which exceeded this threshold. The *in vitro* disintegration times of the films ranged from 15 to 36 seconds, with F5 disintegrating the fastest at 23 seconds. *In vitro* drug release studies revealed that formulation F5 released 95.28% of the drug within 10 minutes, indicating efficient and rapid drug delivery. Thus, formulation F5 was identified as the optimized batch, demonstrating excellent

mechanical and pharmaceutical properties, confirming its potential as a fast-acting oral dosage form for Ketorolac Tromethamine. This dosage form offers significant advantages over conventional tablets, especially for pediatric, geriatric, and dysphagic patients, by eliminating the need for water during administration and enhancing patient compliance. Overall, oral fast dissolving films represent a viable and effective platform for delivering drugs like Ketorolac for immediate relief.

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The physical characterization of FDOFs was carried out by visual inception and the following observation where made. all the formulation (films) where evenly coloured and no migration of colour was observed. The increased thickness of film is attributed to the increase in the amount of HPMC. Formulation F1 to F5 found to be brittle in nature. Formulation F3 was to soft and difficult to handle. And all batches was found to be smooth surface area and all formulations are non tacky.

8.4. Physical characteristics

Table No 12: - Showing Physical Characteristics of Films

Formulation	Appearance	Tack test
F1	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F2	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F3	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F4	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky
F5	Smooth surface and transparent	Non-tacky

- **Surface PH**

Surface pH of all mouth dissolving films prepared by different polymers was found to be in the range of 6.7 to 9.6 pH, which was close to the neutral pH, which indicated that films may have less potential to irritate sublingual mucosa & hence, more acceptable by the patients

- **Weight variation and thickness**

A result showed that as the concentration of polymer increases weight of film also increases or decreases . The weight variation of the formulation was in the range of 50 to 150 mg, which was acceptable. Thickness of mouth dissolving film depends on conc of polymer, thickness of all mouth dissolving film was measured with digital vernier caliper showed thickness value in range of 0.21 to 0.29 mm.

- **Folding Endurance**

Folding endurance gives an indication of brittleness of the film. It was shown that as the concentration of polymer and plasticizer increases, folding Endurance of mouth dissolving film increases. The folding endurance value of the prepared films ranged from 86 to 112, where the results are summarized. The optimized film (F5) has folding endurance value of 85 ± 1 , which was desirable.

- **Drug content uniformity**

All the fast dissolving oral films were found to contain an almost uniform quantity of the drug, as per content uniformity studies indicating reproducibility of the technique. Drug content in the films was evaluated and the values were found to be between 85% to 115%. F4 batch was optimized on the basis high drug content (89.3%)

- **In vitro disintegration studies.**

The disintegrating time of all the formulations was ranges from 15 to 30 see the results were depicted. The disintegration time . of optimized formulation (F5) was found to be 23 sec which was very less and desirable for quick onset of action.

- **Percentage Moisture Loss**

Moisture loss in oral films is a critical parameter to ensure film stability and quality. Ideally, moisture loss should fall within the range of 2–6% for most formulations. Higher moisture loss (above 6%) may indicate over-drying or excessive hygroscopicity, which could affect shelf life and handling. All formulation batches shows the ideal rang but F3 batch shows higher than ideal range.

Table No 13: - Showing Evaluation Of Ketorolac Films

formulation	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Surface pH	7.12	7.09	7.08	7.00	6.72
Weight variation (mg)	78.05±85.55	153.16±148.16	93.05±78.05	53±38	86.38±71.38
Thickness (cm)	0.25	0.23	0.29	0.22	0.21
Folding endurance	87	80	91	81	86
Drug content %	52.11	51.05	23.58	63.82	89.3
% moisture loss	5	3.33	6.67	6	2.5
In vitro disintegration time (sec)	35	30	36	27	23

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

Cumulative % drug release was calculated on the basis of drug content of ketorolac present in the

respective film. The results obtained in the in vitro drug release for the formulations were given. Formulation F1 to F5 shows drug release.

Table No 14: - % Drug Release of Formulation

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0	0	0	0	0
2	22.26%	35.79%	39.20%	43.33%	46.63%
4	35.79%	47.15%	51.18%	48.08%	58.1%
6	47.05%	54.28%	60.78%	60.78%	69.97%
8	56.44%	64.91%	76.58%	71.11%	82.99%
10	69.97%	78.34%	89.18%	77.00%	95.28%

DISCUSSION: -

The ultimate aim of this present work was to develop immediate release drug delivery system of ketorolac. The In vitro cumulative drug release profile of these formulations showed up to 95.28%

release in 10 min the formulation F5 showed satisfactory drug release in 10 min i.e. 95.28% which is considered as an optimized batch. During the study concluded that the film were dissolves immediately and gives highest % drug release up to 10 min.

Fig No 15: - Cumulative % Drug Release of F1 To F5